

Review

Optimizing Trauma Patient Management: A Collaborative Approach Between Emergency Medicine, General Surgery And Orthopedics Departments

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Abstract: Objective: To explore the effect of multi-disciplinary team (MDT) in MIHS Provincial hospitals on severe trauma patients. Method: This study reviewed the treatment of patients with severe trauma in MIHS Provincial Hospital of Janakpurdham, Nepal from January 2023 to May 2024. The patients' gender, age, injury mechanism, etc.; the start indicators: the Glasgow coma scale (GCS), trauma index (TI), injury severity score (ISS); the start related indicators: time for activation, time for MDT to arrive, time for CT scan, time for damage control surgery; patient treatment and prognosis: ICU (intensive care unit) length of stay, number of cured and discharged patients, number of dead cases, number of patients transferred to rehabilitation hospital, were all analyzed. It discussed the composition of MDT, the initiation scheme, the indicators of initiation of MDT for severe trauma, and analyzed the correlation between the application of MDT and the prognosis of patients. Result: From January 2023 to May 2024, 112 trauma patients were treated by MDT (Emergency Medicine, General Surgery and Orthopedics Departments) in MIHS Provincial Hospital Janakpurdham, Nepal. There were 69 males and 43 females. The minimum age was 15 years, the maximum age was 89 years, most of them were 36-55 years old. The main injury mechanism was traffic accident injury. The GCS, TI, ISS were 13.0 ± 2.9 , 13.0 ± 2.8 , and 21.5 ± 11.9 , respectively. It took 3.7 ± 0.8 minutes to start the call, 6.1 ± 0.9 minutes for MDT personnel to arrive at the emergency rescue area, 72.3 ± 21.1 minutes for fast CT and 190.2 ± 92.5 minutes for injury control operation. All the hospitalized patients were treated effectively. ICU (Intensive care unit) hospitalization time was 12.6 ± 6.7 days. 55 discharged patients were cured, 5 died (1 died of hemorrhagic shock, 4 died of severe brain injury) and 52 transferred to rehabilitation hospital. Conclusion: The treatment of severe trauma patients by MDT (Emergency Medicine, General Surgery and Orthopedics Departments) in MIHS provincial hospitals can greatly improve the ability and level of treatment of severe trauma patients, improvement for the lack of treatment of severe trauma especially multiple trauma patients in hospitals and improve the treatment effect of severe trauma patients. It provides a reference model for large hospitals to treat patients with severe trauma and multiple trauma with collaborative approach.

Keywords: trauma, emergency medicine, general surgery, orthopedics, MDT

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Introduction

Injuries are among the leading causes of death and disability in the world, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where more than 90% of the world's injury-related deaths occur [1]. In such settings, preventive health initiatives are limited, and healthcare systems may be poorly prepared to meet this challenge [2,3]. Similar to other LMICs, injuries are a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in Nepal. The estimated proportion of deaths due to injury in Nepal increased from 6.31% to 9.21% between 1990 and 2017 [4]. The injury mortality rate was estimated at 59 per 100,000 population in 2017, doubling the rate calculated from the 2001 Nepal census (30 per 100,000 population) [5]. Young and middle-aged adults experience a greater burden of injuries than other age groups, and there will be more young and middle-aged adults with disabilities secondary to injury in the future [6].

Case series suggest that road traffic injuries (RTIs) are the most common cause of trauma in Nepal [7,8], while falls, burns, poisoning, occupational, and animal-related injuries are other frequent causes [8,9]. The economic and social costs of these injuries can have a serious impact on the individuals, their families, and wider society. In Nepal, the total costs of RTIs alone were estimated at USD 122.88 million, which is equivalent to 1.52% of the gross national product [10]. Injury prevention is relatively new to the public health agenda for Nepal, and the burden of injuries is not well quantified, with most of the literature reporting small hospital case series [11]. Sources of routine injury data collection are also limited [12]. Therefore, there is little evidence to understand the actual burden of injury, the associated risk factors, or the populations at risk. The World Health Organisation defines injury surveillance as "the ongoing systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of injury data, for use in planning, implementation, and evaluation of prevention activities [13]". Hospital-based surveillance systems have been an integral component in improving trauma care in high-income countries [14]. Trauma registries have been successfully established in some LMICs [15,16,17,18]. However, they focus on improving hospital care and outcomes rather than identifying the epidemiology of a condition and prevention opportunities [19,20]. MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal has established a multidisciplinary collaborative diagnosis and treatment (multidisciplinary team, MDT) model for the treatment of severe trauma patients, and on this basis, it treats severe trauma patients. This study retrospectively analyzed the treatment of severe trauma patients admitted to Provincial Hospital in the past one years to explore the treatment effect of this model on severe trauma patients, better promote the standardization of severe trauma treatment, and aim to establish a scientific and standardized severe trauma treatment system.

Research Methodology

The data of patients with severe trauma who were admitted to the Emergency department of MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal from January 2023 to May 2024 and initiated the MDT process were selected for retrospective analysis and a total of 112 cases were collected. Analysis of medical records Statistics of patients' gender, age, injury mechanism and other general information. Analysis of start-up indicators Statistics of patients' GCS (Glasgow coma scale) score, TI (trauma index) score, and ISS (injury severity score) score. Analysis of start-up related indicators Statistics of MDT start-up call time (the time from patient admission to call of MDT team), time from call to arrival, time to complete whole body rapid CT (time from admission to completion of CT) and time to start damage control surgery (time from admission to start of surgery). Analysis of patient treatment and prognosis Statistics of ICU hospital stay, number of

cured and discharged patients, number of deaths, and number of patients transferred to rehabilitation hospitals. The MDT team of MIHS Provincial Hospital is composed of experts from the emergency department, anesthesiology department, critical care medicine department, trauma orthopedics department, general surgery department, neurosurgery department, urology department and other departments. When a patient who meets the activation criteria is admitted to the hospital, the emergency department calls the MDT team, and the full-time staff of the MIHS is responsible for organizing the MDT discussion, assisting in formulating the best treatment plan, and following up the operation to ensure the smooth progress of the rescue. In case of traumatic events and any of the following situations, the MDT team should be called immediately: (1) systolic blood pressure <90 mmHg; (2) respiration <9 times/min or >29 times/min; (3) heart rate >120 times/min; (4) GCS score <14 points (suspected skull fracture, epileptic seizure, pupil disparity, localized neurological dysfunction); (5) TI score ≥10 points; (6) moderate or above injuries in more than two departments. Traumatic events include: (1) penetrating injuries of related parts: including head, face, neck, chest, abdomen, limbs and pelvis; (2) fractures: open or closed skull fractures, pelvic fractures, two or more long bone fractures, spinal cord injuries (any trauma accompanied by neurological deficits, such as paralysis or tingling), flail chest, etc.; (3) limb amputation caused by trauma; (4) explosion injuries, crush injuries, gunshot injuries, severe burns, etc.; (5) traffic accidents: high-speed impact injuries (speed >40 km/h), or pedestrian-motor vehicle collision (speed>30 km/h), severe deformity of the vehicle, invasion and squeezing of the vehicle passenger compartment, death of other passengers in the vehicle, rollover of the vehicle (including passengers), and rescue time>20 min; (6) fall from height: height>3 m (children need to consider their age and height); (7) air rescue transfer: including patients who maintain vital signs through blood transfusion at the scene or in an outpatient medical institution, and patients who have been intubated or have respiratory safety problems [2,3]. After being treated by the MDT team, patients who meet one of the following conditions should be admitted to the trauma treatment center ward for further treatment: (1) ISS score ≥16 points, AIS (abbreviated injury scale) score ≥4 points; (2) multiple injuries (more than two anatomical parts of the ISS): ISS anatomical sites are divided into six parts: head and neck (including cervical spine), face (including cranium), chest (including thoracic spine and diaphragm), abdomen and pelvis (including lumbar spine), limbs and pelvis, body surface and others; (3) single injury, accompanied by severe instability of vital signs requiring emergency treatment; (4) high-energy direct violent injury (patients whose diagnosis is unclear at the first time). Clinical data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, general data such as patient age, gender, and injury mechanism were described using count data, and MDT initiation indicators and related indicators were expressed as mean ± standard deviation.

Results

From January 2023 to May 2024, MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpurdham, Nepal initiated the MDT process to treat 112 patients with severe trauma, including 69 males and 43 females, aged 15 to 89 years old, mostly aged 36 to 55 years old. The injury mechanism was mainly traffic accident injury (Table 1). The GCS score of the patients upon admission was 13.0±2.9, TI score was 13.0±2.8, and ISS score was 21.5±11.9. After the MDT rescue process was initiated, the call time was (3.7±0.8) min, the arrival time was (6.1±0.9) min, the rapid CT time was (72.3±21.1) min, and the damage control surgery time was (190.2±92.5) min (Table 2). All patients who came to the hospital were effectively treated, and the ICU stay time was (12.6±6.7) d. 55 patients were cured and discharged, 5 died (1 died of hemorrhagic shock, 4 died of severe craniocerebral injury), and 52 patients were transferred to rehabilitation hospitals.

Table.1 The characteristics of severe trauma patients

Items	Numbers
Gender	
Male	69
Female	43
Age	
15-35	12
36-55	48

56-75	39
>75	13
Mechanics of injury	
Traffic accidents	52
Fall	29
Explosion, crush, injury	19
Others	12

Table.2 Evaluation of related indicators after start-up of MDT

Indicators	Data
Activation indicators	
GCS	13.0±2.9
TI	13.0±3.8
ISS	21.5±11.9
Activation related indicators/min	
Time for activation	3.7±0.8
Time for MDT to arrive	6.1±0.9
Time for CT scan	72.3±21.1
Time for damage control surgery	190.2±92.5

GCS:glasgow coma scale; TI: trauma index; ISS: injury severity score; MDT: multidisciplinary team.

Discussion

Severe trauma, represented by multiple injuries, often involves multiple systems and multiple parts, requiring the participation of multiple surgical specialists in injury assessment, emergency surgery, and subsequent planned staged surgery, thus requiring the participation and guidance of a multidisciplinary team. However, the current development of hospital disciplines has moved towards specialization and specialization. Traditional departments are unable to cope with the needs of severe trauma treatment, and no single department has the ability to treat severe multiple injuries [4]. In addition, comprehensive tertiary hospitals mainly treat patients with chronic diseases, and emergency trauma patients are often not taken seriously. Beds are mostly reserved for routine patients, and emergency patients are often "hard to find a bed". Based on the current hospital bed management model and the limitations of bed turnover rate, Patients must make an appointment to be admitted to the hospital, and beds cannot be reserved for emergency patients. The mode of ICU admission of patients also often needs to correspond to a certain specialty. The trauma treatment center should have facilities and equipment and capabilities to comprehensively handle severe trauma, including pre-hospital trauma emergency, emergency, trauma surgery, surgical anesthesia, ICU, imaging medicine, laboratory medicine, blood transfusion and other trauma medicine core team disciplines, and an in-hospital trauma treatment system supported by the in-hospital trauma treatment system[5]. Its basic characteristics are "substantiated multidisciplinary collaborative diagnosis and treatment" and "centralized ward admission of patients with severe trauma such as multiple injuries"[6]. It solves multiple specialty problems at the same time and is not limited by conventional bed performance, which greatly improves the treatment level of severe trauma patients. The MDT team of the trauma treatment center should include emergency surgery, trauma orthopedics, neurosurgery, thoracic surgery, general surgery, critical care medicine, imaging, anesthesia, etc. Most of the team members are young and middle-aged technical backbones. In addition to having rich clinical experience, they often face emergency, long-term or even all-night operations, which requires strong physical fitness. They should be different from other MDT teams (mainly composed of experienced experts) and need to be on call at any time. They can come and fight when they are called. They cannot adopt the form of weekly scheduled discussions, but 24/7 h on-call form, and undertake out-of-hospital emergency and disaster medical rescue tasks. In the emergency treatment stage, multidisciplinary collaborative injury assessment, emergency treatment and surgery to save lives are required. In the intensive care stage, multidisciplinary

collaborative re-assessment of injuries, resuscitation and organ support, planned or unplanned staged definitive surgery are required. The MDT organization must have a leader, a meeting chairman, participating experts and backbones, a coordinator, etc., and should have a complete work system, including emergency work plans for emergencies, bed management and use system, multidisciplinary joint rounds system, preoperative discussion system, medical staff duty management system, surgical classification management regulations and procedures, information system entry management regulations, etc. In this study, MIHS Provincial Hospital drew on foreign experience and combined with actual conditions to formulate MDT initiation standards and patient admission standards. After the MDT process was initiated, the time to complete rapid CT was (72.3 ± 21.1) min, and the time to start damage control surgery was (190.2 ± 92.5) min, which improves the treatment efficiency of patients with severe trauma. All patients in this study were effectively treated, with 5 deaths and a mortality rate of 4.5%, which greatly improved the treatment outcomes of patients with severe trauma. The advantage of the MDT model is that patients can take effective examination and intervention measures as soon as possible after injury, which is particularly important for the initial management of patients with severe trauma and stabilizing vital signs. Multidisciplinary comprehensive diagnosis and treatment can formulate feasible diagnosis and treatment plans in the first place, providing a solid guarantee for subsequent surgical treatment. The main cause of death of patients in this study was severe craniocerebral injury. According to the experience of our team, severe craniocerebral injury is one of the important factors for poor prognosis, which needs to be further studied. Literature reports that under the operation of the MDT model in trauma treatment centers, the time for patients to be diagnosed after arriving at the hospital is shortened, the length of ICU stay and the average length of stay are shortened, and the survival rate of patients is improved [7]. There are also reports abroad that multidisciplinary diagnosis and treatment shortens the time for diagnosis, reduces the delayed diagnosis rate and mortality rate of severe lesions, and can improve the treatment efficiency of trauma patients [8]. In 2018, the National Health Commission issued the "Notice on Further Improving Trauma Treatment Capabilities", and Annex 3 of the notice lists the medical quality control indicators of trauma treatment centers [1]. In this study, combined with the requirements of the notice and the characteristics of MDT, relevant indicators were selected, including start-up indicators (GCS score, TI score, ISS score), start-up related indicators (start-up call time, arrival time, completion time of rapid CT, start time of damage control surgery), and patient prognosis (ICU hospitalization time, number of deaths, etc.) to evaluate the quality of treatment. At present, the country has not yet standardized and quantified the relevant quality control indicators. The results of this study only represent the time control of treatment under the conditions of MIHS Hospital. At present, the construction of several major trauma treatment centers in our country has significantly improved the treatment capabilities of severe polytrauma. MDT has achieved initial results, but there are still shortcomings. The development of MDT is limited to large medical centers, and there is uneven regional development; the organization Form is greater than content, misunderstanding, and lack of inclusion criteria for trauma MDT; some hospitals have problems such as limited support, imperfect infrastructure, and insufficient incentive mechanisms [5]. Although many severe trauma treatment models have been established abroad for reference, Due to different national conditions, international treatment models cannot be directly copied [9]. The launch, organization and standardized implementation of MDT still need to formulate relevant standards at the national level and increase the standardized training of trauma treatment center practitioners, thereby improving the overall capabilities of the team. At the same time, the hospitals where trauma treatment centers at all levels are located should adhere to the development of trauma treatment as the key direction to provide a guarantee for the organization and implementation of MDT.

Conclusion

This study still has limitations. First of all, this study is a retrospective study and lacks control group data. Clinical controlled trials need to be designed in the future. Secondly, the relationship between severe craniocerebral injury and patient mortality requires further research. In summary, the trauma treatment of MIHS hospital uses the MDT model to treat severe trauma patients, which can significantly improve the treatment capabilities and level of severe trauma

patients, improvement for the lack of detailed treatment of severe trauma and polytrauma patients in hospitals. This study provides a reference model for the treatment of patients with severe trauma and polytrauma in general hospitals and the construction of trauma treatment centers.

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